

Some Observations on the Gattermann Reaction of Xylenols

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The Gattermann reaction on 2,3-, 2,4-, 2,5-, 2,6-, 3,4-, and 3,5-xylenols has been investigated and the identity of different aldehydes obtained has been established.

During the course of some synthetic work, we investigated the Gattermann aldehyde synthesis with different xylenols. The data available in literature are incomplete since with each of the xylenols, a mixture of aldehydes is obtained which do not seem to have been separated and some of which are hitherto unknown.

Table I describes the different aldehydes which can be obtained from the various xylenols.

TABLE I

Xylenol.	Corresponding aldehydes		
2,3-	1-OH-2,3-diMe- benzaldehyde-4 (I)	1-OH-2,3,-diMe- benzaldehyde-5 (II)	1-OH-2,3-diMe- benzaldehyde-6 (III)
2,4-	1-OH-2,4-diMe- benzaldehyde-6 (IV)	1-OH-2,4-diMe- benzaldehyde-3 (V)	1-OH-2,4-diMe- benzaldehyde-5 (VI)
2,5-	1-OH-2,5-diMe- benzaldehyde-4 (VII)	1-OH-2,5-diMe- benzaldehyde-6 (VIII)	1-OH-2,5-diMe- benzaldehyde-3 (IX)
2,6-	1-OH-2,6-diMe- benzaldehyde-4 (X)	1-OH-2,6-diMe- benzaldehyde-3 (XI)	..
3,4-	1-OH-3,4-diMe- benzaldehyde-2 (XII)	1-OH-3,4-diMe- benzaldehyde-6 (XIII)	1-OH-3,4-diMe- benzaldehyde-5 (XIV)
3,5-	1-OH-3,5-diMe- benzaldehyde-4 (XV)	1-OH-3,5-diMe- benzaldehyde-2 (XVI)	

The Gattermann reaction on the xylenols was carried out by passing dry hydrogen chloride in a benzene solution of the xylene in presence of zinc cyanide and anhydrous aluminium chloride.

With 2,3-xylene, product (I), which was prepared previously by the Gattermann reaction¹, and (III) could be isolated, whereas (II) was not obtained at all. As expected, (III)

1. Gattermann, *Annalen*, 1907, 357, 323.

was steam-distillable and gave a violet coloration with ferric chloride solution. It could be oxidised with silver nitrate in alkaline medium to the unknown 2-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylbenzoic acid.

With 2,4-xylenol, the Gattermann reaction yielded (IV) as the main product which was prepared by Bamberger and Weiler² from dimethylindazole by the action of acids. Its identity as (IV) was confirmed by preparation of its known oxime² and its oxidation to the known 2-hydroxy-3,5-dimethylbenzoic acid². It is easily volatile with steam and develops a violet coloration with ferric chloride. The second product of the reaction, which was isolated in very small amounts, on oxidation with silver nitrate in alkaline medium yielded a small amount of an acid which was identified as 5-hydroxy-2,4-dimethylbenzoic acid by a mixed melting point with the specimen prepared as described in literature³. The result confirms the structure (VI) for the aldehyde.

With 2,5-xylenol, the Gattermann reaction yielded both (VII) and (VIII). The former aldehyde has been previously reported by Gattermann¹, whereas the latter has been obtained by Wynberg⁴ by the Reimer-Tiemann reaction on the xylenol. The isomer (IX) could not be isolated.

With 2,6-xylenol, a mixture of (X) and (XI) is formed and the two are separated by steam distillation. The aldehyde (X) has been prepared by Gattermann¹ and (XI) is hitherto unknown. On oxidation with silver nitrate in alkaline solution, it gave 2,4-dimethyl-3-hydroxybenzoic acid, which is unknown.

The Gattermann reaction with 3,4-xylenol afforded a mixture of (XII) and (XIII), both of which distilled along with steam to afford a solid mixed with an oil. The solid after crystallisation from ethanol melted at 70° and was identified as (XIII) by preparation of its known phenylhydrazone¹ and confirmed by conversion to the corresponding acid^{5,6}. The oily portion of the steam-distillate was distilled under vacuum and treated with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine when two crystalline derivatives of m. p. 261° and 149-50° were isolated. The former derivative was found to be identical with that of (XIII) by a mixed m. p. determination. The second derivative could be of the aldehyde (XII), which was prepared by Clayton⁵ and also by Marvel and Higgins⁶ by different methods.

With 3,5-xylenol, a mixture of (XV) and (XVI) was obtained and the two isomers were separated by steam distillation. Both were prepared by Wilds and Djerassi⁷, employing the Gattermann reaction. The oxidation of (XV) with silver nitrate in alkaline solution afforded the corresponding acid in a poor yield.

As a point of interest, it may be noted that whereas the oxidation of CHO to COOH generally proceeds smoothly with silver nitrate in alkaline solution, the same is rendered extremely difficult when the CHO is flanked on either side by methyl groups.

2. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1898, 58, 351.

3. Meldrum and Kapadia, *this Journal*, 1932, 9, 490.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4998.

5. Clayton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1404.

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2218.

7. *Ibid.*, 1946, 68, 1862.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Method for the Gattermann Reaction on Xylenols

Through an ice-cooled and well-stirred mixture of the xylene (25 g.), anhydrous zinc cyanide (4 g.), and dry thiophene-free benzene dry HCl gas was passed for about 30 mins. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (70 g.) was added to the reaction mixture and its temperature was gradually raised to 40-45°, while HCl gas was passed into the mixture and continued for 4 to 5 hours, the mixture being stirred throughout. After leaving overnight, the benzene was decanted and the imide chloride washed well with benzene and then decomposed with water. The mixture was subjected to steam distillation, when one of the isomers generally distilled. It was isolated by extraction with ether. The residue from the steam distillation was also worked up by extraction with ether.

2,3-Xylenol.—The Gattermann reaction with the xylene (15g.) yielded a mixture of (I) (9 g.) and (III) (1.5 g.). The aldehyde (III) was isolated from the steam distillate as an oil, 2,4-DNP of which after crystallisation from acetic acid melted at 274-75°. (Found: N, 16.6. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3N_4$ requires N, 16.9%).

The aldehyde (I) was isolated from the residue from the steam distillate and crystallised from toluene in leaflets, m. p. 172° (lit. m. p. 172°).

Oxidation of (III) to 2-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethylbenzoic Acid.—To a well-stirred mixture of (III, 1g.) in water (12 ml) containing NaOH (1.53 g.) was added a solution of silver nitrate (1.02 g.) in water (4.6 ml), previously warmed to 55°. The temperature of the mixture rose to about 85° and metallic silver was precipitated as a spongy mass. The stirring was continued for further $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and the mixture filtered while hot. The alkaline filtrate was acidified by passing SO_2 , when a white solid (600 mg.) separated on cooling. On sublimation under vacuum, colorless needles of m. p. 190-91° were obtained. (Found: C, 65.3; H, 6.2. $C_9H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 65.0; H, 6.0%).

2,4-Xylenol.—The Gattermann reaction with the xylene (25 g.) yielded about 10g. of (IV) as an oil, obtained from the steam distillate. Its oxime crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 138-39° (lit. m. p. 138-39°). Its 2,4-DNP crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 176°. (Found: N, 16.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3N_4$ requires N, 16.9%).

On oxidation with silver nitrate and alkali, it yielded 2-hydroxy-3,5-dimethylbenzoic acid, crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m. p. 177-78° (lit. m. p. 179°).

From the residue of the steam distillate after extraction with ether was obtained a dark-coloured pasty material (2 g.). It gave a 2,4-DNP, which after crystallisation from acetic acid melted at 216°. (Found: N, 16.6. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3N_4$ requires N, 16.9%).

On oxidation with silver nitrate in alkaline solution, as described before, it yielded an acid, which after crystallisation from toluene and sublimation under vacuum had m. p. 169-70°. It was identified by mixed m. p. determination as 5-hydroxy-2,4-dimethylbenzoic acid, prepared as described by Meldrum and Kapadia³.

2,5-Xylenol.—The Gattermann reaction with this xylene (15g.) afforded a mixture of (VII) (3.5 g.) and (VIII) (4 g.). The latter obtained from the steam distillate was crystal-

lised from petroleum ether, m.p. 67° (lit. m.p. 62-63°). The residue from steam distillate after crystallisation from water gave (VII), m.p. 132-33° (lit. m.p. 132-33°).

2,6-Xylenol.—The Gattermann synthesis with this xylenol (16 g.) afforded a mixture of (X) (9 g.) and (XI) (4 g.). The aldehyde (X) was obtained from the residue of the steam distillate and crystallised from dilute ethanol in brown needles, m.p. 114-15° (lit. m.p. 116°).

From the steam distillate the aldehyde (XI) was obtained in the form of an oil, 2,4-DNP of which crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 234-35°. (Found: N, 16.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires N, 16.9%).

On oxidation with silver nitrate in alkaline medium, as described before, aldehyde (XI) gave an acid, 3-hydroxy-2,4-dimethylbenzoic acid, as colorless needles, m.p. 276-77°. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 6.5. $C_9H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 65.0; H, 6.0%).

2,4-Xylenol.—The Gattermann reaction with this xylenol (25 g.) gave on steam distillation first a solid (9 g.) and afterwards an oil (3.5 g.). The solid was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 70° (lit. m.p. 71°). It gave a colorless phenylhydrazone, m.p. 195° (lit. m.p. 195°). Its 2,4-DNP was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 269°. (Found: N, 16.5. $C_{15}H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires N, 16.9%).

The oily steam distillate failed to furnish a phenylhydrazone, but afforded a very small amount of a 2,4-DNP of m.p. 269° which was found to be identical with the same derivative obtained from (XIII). The oil was therefore distilled under vacuum and the fraction boiling at 118-21°/2 mm was collected. It was treated with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in ethanolic solution when a small amount of a solid separated. This was found to be identical with the 2,4-DNP from (XIII). From the ethanol-soluble portion another crystalline derivative was isolated which after crystallisation from acetic acid melted at 149-50°. (Found: N, 16.8. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 16.9%). This derivative could be of the aldehyde (XII), which was described by Marvel and Higgins⁶ as a solid of m.p. 70°.

3,5-Xylenol.—The Gattermann reaction on this xylenol (12 g.) gave (XVI) (3 g.) from the steam distillate. After distillation at 84-90°/10mm, it solidified to a colorless mass, m.p. 47-48° (lit. m.p. 47-48°). From the residue, (XV) was isolated (6 g.) which was crystallised from ethanol in prisms, m.p. 195-96° (lit. m.p. 195-96°).

Oxidation of (XV) to 4-Hydroxy-2,6-dimethylbenzoic Acid.—The oxidation of (XV) with silver nitrate and alkali was carried out as before, but the time of heating had to be increased from 30 minutes to 10 hours. Moreover, the yield of the acid was very low (400 mg. from 3g. of XV). The acid was crystallised from water, m.p. 185° (lit.⁸ m.p. 185°).